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THE ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF PNEUMONIA, MODERN DIAGNOSIS AND DIAGNOSTIC METHODS

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Abstract Pneumonia is an acute infectious inflammation of the lungs, which can pass without a trace or lead to death. In some cases, vaccination, as well as general precautions, can help prevent the disease. Pneumonia is a group of inflammatory diseases of the lungs, which are often caused by the penetration of infectious agents into the respiratory tract: bacteria, viruses, fungi. Less commonly, non-infectious pneumonia may develop. This happens in autoimmune diseases or when a foreign object or fluid accidentally ends up in the lungs. The lungs are made up of small air chambers called alveoli, which are filled with air with each breath. Through them, oxygen enters the blood and carbon dioxide is released again. With pneumonia, the alveoli are inflamed, fluid or pus appears in them, as a result of which the amount of air that can be breathed decreases and less oxygen enters the blood. As a result, a person cannot breathe normally, he does not have enough air.

Keywords: causes, transmission, mechanism of development, symptoms, diagnosis, treatment and prevention.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation does not necessarily affect the entire lung - usually individual lesions appear, segments or lobes are affected.

Depending on the size of the lesion, the pathology is divided into focal, unilateral or bilateral. In addition, community-acquired and hospital-acquired pneumonia are distinguished. The difference between them is the danger of the pathogen. Hospital-acquired pneumonia is more difficult and longer to treat because hospital-acquired bacteria are usually resistant to most known antibiotics.

Spread

Pneumonia is one of the most common acute infectious diseases. According to the 2021 clinical guidelines, the prevalence of community-acquired pneumonia in 2019 was 410 per 100,000 population. The highest rate of the disease is observed in the Urals, the Far East and Siberia.

ICD code

In the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, Tenth Revision (ICD-10), pneumonia (depending on the causes, location and extent) is designated by different codes.

Thus, codes starting with the English letter J indicate pneumonia caused by viruses, bacteria and fungi. For example, J12.0 is adenovirus pneumonia, and J16.0 is chlamydial pneumonia. Codes starting with English P are congenital infectious pneumonia. For example, P23.2 - congenital pneumonia caused by staphylococci or P23.5 - congenital pneumonia caused by *Pseudomonas*.

Causes of pneumonia

Pneumonia can occur for many reasons: bacterial, viral or fungal infection, allergies, inhalation of toxic substances or vomiting.

The severity of the disease and the method of its treatment largely depend on what factor caused the pneumonia. However, the symptoms for all types of pneumonia are the same: cough, weakness, shortness of breath.

Bacterial infection

Pneumonia caused by a bacterial infection is the most common type of pneumonia.

Common bacteria that cause pneumonia are:

pneumococcus (*S. pneumoniae*);

mycoplasma pneumoniae (*M. pneumoniae*);

chlamydia pneumoniae (*C. pneumoniae*);

Haemophilus influenzae (*H. influenzae*);

Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*);

Legionella pneumoniae (*L. pneumophila*).

Usually, these bacteria cause pneumonia if the body is weakened - for example, there was a recent acute respiratory viral infection or other infection, a person underwent surgery or experienced severe stress. In addition, the immune system can work at half capacity due to poor nutrition, age, smoking and chronic alcohol abuse.

Viral infection

Pneumonia caused by a viral infection is often diagnosed in children under 5 years of age. As a rule, it is easier and rarely leads to complications.

Common viruses that cause pneumonia:

A and B influenza viruses,
coronaviruses,
respiratory syncytial virus,
parainfluenza viruses,
adenovirus,
herpes virus,
rhinovirus,
metapneumovirus,
bocavirus.

Most people with viral pneumonia will recover within 1-3 weeks without treatment, although in some cases the disease becomes severe and requires hospitalization. This usually occurs in people with weakened immune systems.

Fungal infection

Fungal pneumonia is more common in people with chronic diseases or severely weakened immune systems, such as HIV patients. In addition, those who regularly inhale fungal spores from contaminated soil or animal feces, such as farm and poultry farm workers, are at increased risk of infection.

Farmers and livestock workers are at risk of developing fungal pneumonia

Common fungi that cause pneumonia:

Pneumocystis jirovecii (pneumocystis pneumonia);

Coccidioidosis (coccidioidosis);

Histoplasma capsulatum (histoplasmosis);

Cryptococcus (cryptococcosis).

Aspiration pneumonia occurs when foreign substances - particles of food, drinks or vomit - accidentally enter the respiratory tract. A foreign object can enter the lungs, rot and cause infection. This usually happens if a person's gag or cough reflex is impaired, such as traumatic brain injury, alcohol or psychoactive substance poisoning, or anesthesia.

To prevent aspiration pneumonia, patients are advised not to eat or drink before surgery.

Risk factors for pneumonia

Pneumonia can develop in anyone, but the lungs are most often inflamed in children under the age of 2 and in adults over 65 years of age. There are other risk factors.

Hospitalization.

Due to the disease, weakened immunity fights worse against pathogenic bacteria, viruses and fungi, so the probability of getting pneumonia in the hospital is very high. The risk is even higher if the person is in intensive care and on a ventilator.

Weakened immune system.

People living with HIV, chemotherapy patients, and people who have had organ or tissue transplants are at increased risk of pneumonia. In addition, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), heart disease, diabetes mellitus, anemia and other chronic pathologies reduce the protective capacity of the immune system.

Difficulty swallowing.

Difficulty swallowing after Parkinson's disease or a stroke or injury can cause food or drink to enter the lungs, increasing the risk of developing aspiration pneumonia.

Occupational hazards.

Inhaling animal feces, contaminated soil, and industrial toxins and chemicals increases the likelihood of developing inflammation in the lungs.

In addition, the risk of illness is high for those who do not eat enough or monotonously, smoke or regularly abuse alcohol, because the body is weakened and cannot cope with defense against possible pathogens.

How is pneumonia transmitted?

Viruses, bacteria and fungi are transmitted from person to person, which can cause inflammation in the lungs. Thus, some viruses and bacteria can be spread through the air through small droplets from the nose and mouth when talking, coughing or sneezing.

To prevent infection, it is recommended to stay at a distance of at least 1.5 meters from the patient

In addition, pathogens can settle on surrounding objects such as doorknobs or elevator buttons. If a person touches an infected surface and then touches their face, they are at risk of contracting the infection.

The causative agent of fungal pneumonia lives in soil, rotting food and animal waste. Fungi grow rapidly, multiply and release spores that float in the air and are easily inhaled into the human body.

Every day, a person inhales hundreds of potentially dangerous pathogens, but rarely gets sick: the immune system fights pathogens well.

Aspiration pneumonia is not transmitted, it develops only after inhalation of foreign objects or liquids.

Is pneumonia contagious?

Pneumonia is a group of acute infectious (mainly bacterial) diseases that differ in their causes, mechanism of development, and morphological characteristics.

Given that pneumonia is often caused by viruses and bacteria, a person with pneumonia can be dangerous to others because pathogens are easily transmitted through the air or left on objects.

Types of pneumonia due to development:

pneumococcus;

streptococcus;

mycoplasma;

Pneumonia caused by Haemophilus influenzae;

pneumonia due to measles;

pneumonia due to influenza;

pneumonia due to coronavirus infection;

undiagnosed pneumonia, etc.

Types of pneumonia according to the extent of damage:

focal - affects one area or focus in the lungs;

segmental - one or more segments of the lung are affected;

lobar - one part of the lung is affected;

total - all lungs covered.

Depending on where the pneumonia appeared, it is divided into acquired in the hospital and in the community. Community-acquired pneumonia is any pneumonia that develops outside of a hospital or less than 48 hours after a person is hospitalized. All others are classified as hospital-acquired or hospital-acquired pneumonia.

Mechanism of development of pneumonia

When pneumonia occurs, pathogens enter the human respiratory tract. In response to this, an inflammatory process occurs. As a result of inflammation, the alveoli are filled with fluid, making it difficult for a person to breathe. The larger the lesion, the more difficult it is to breathe: sometimes it may seem as if there is no air at all.

Symptoms of pneumonia

Not all types of pneumonia show clear symptoms. The disease may resemble a common cold or be detected only on a CT scan.

Characteristic symptoms of pneumonia in adults:

temperature above 38 ° C;

weakness even without physical activity;

cough with sputum, which does not improve;

wheezing;

chest pain or heaviness;

shortness of breath;

sweating and shivering;

headache;

loss of appetite;

nausea, vomiting or diarrhea.

In people over 65 years of age, pneumonia can occur without fever and is manifested by confusion and memory impairment.

Blue lips are a sign of oxygen deficiency due to pneumonia

In young children, pneumonia may not manifest itself as a cough. However, if the child is always lying down or seems lethargic, you should be careful. In children over 5 years old, after the characteristic symptoms of ARVI, cough and shortness of breath may appear: runny nose, sneezing, weakness.

Complications of pneumonia

Most people recover from pneumonia without developing complications. However, if a person does not seek medical help for a long time, does not follow the doctor's instructions, or is at risk, then the probability of developing complications increases.

Possible complications of pneumonia:

bacteremia and sepsis. Bacteria from the lungs can enter the bloodstream and cause a widespread infection of the body;

pleural effusion - pathological accumulation of fluid in the lungs. In this case, the fluid cannot flow out on its own or must be drained;

lung abscess - the formation of a cavity filled with pus;

respiratory failure.

Diagnosis of pneumonia

During the examination, the doctor may suspect pneumonia. Further studies are required to determine the exact location and cause of inflammation, as well as to prescribe treatment.

When to see a doctor

Pneumonia often develops after a recent cold or other infection. However, this is not necessary. If the condition worsens after a temporary improvement, the cough becomes stronger and more painful, the sputum becomes sticky and cloudy, chest pain, shortness of breath and severe weakness appear, you should consult a general practitioner.

A person with pneumonia does not necessarily have all of these symptoms. If there are at least two, you should not delay visiting a specialist.

breathing became very frequent (more than 30 breaths per minute);

pressure dropped below 90/60 mm Hg. Art.;

confusion appeared: lethargy, dizziness, inability to answer simple questions;

a foreign object or fluid may have entered the lungs.

During the examination, the doctor will determine the details of the medical history, listen to your breathing, and perform pulse oximetry to determine the level of oxygen in the blood.

Normally, the amount of oxygen in the blood is 95-100%, if it is below 92%, it is an indication for urgent hospitalization.

Further confirmatory studies are also required. They help distinguish pneumonia from acute respiratory viral infections, influenza or bronchitis.

Laboratory diagnosis of pneumonia

Usually, all patients with suspected pneumonia are given a blood test by a doctor to assess their general health. A high level of white blood cells and ESR is a characteristic sign of infection.

Complete blood count with leukocyte count and ESR, smear microscopy for pathological changes in leukocyte count (venous blood)

A clinical blood test is a blood test that allows you to assess your general health, detect inflammation, bacterial, viral and fungal infections, as well as help diagnose anemia, diseases of the hematopoietic organs, allergic reactions and autoimmune diseases.

Instrumental diagnosis of pneumonia

A doctor may order a chest X-ray or computed tomography (CT) scan to assess the extent of the injury and identify areas of inflammation.

Bronchoscopy makes it possible to detect foreign objects in the bronchi. During the test, a thin tube with a camera at the end is inserted into the airway through the nose or mouth and checked for blockage. During the procedure, the doctor may take a sample of fluid or tissue for analysis in the laboratory.

How to distinguish pneumonia from ARVI, flu and bronchitis

To distinguish pneumonia from acute respiratory viral infections, flu, bronchitis or other diseases affecting the lungs, imaging studies - X-rays, fluorography and computer tomography allow. In the photos, you can see infiltrates, which are characteristic of pneumonia - accumulation of fluid in the lungs.

Treatment of pneumonia

Treatment tactics depend on the cause and severity of the disease. If the inflammation is small and the pneumonia is mild, then the person stays at home. Severe inflammation is treated in a hospital. In addition, people at risk of hospitalization: over 65 years old, young children, as well as those with cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, bronchial asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are hospitalized.

Bacterial pneumonia is treated with antibiotics. Relief usually occurs in the first 2-3 days, but some symptoms, such as extreme fatigue.

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